

A Case Study of Canine Transmissible Venereal Tumour in Pomeranian Bitch

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Abstract: *Canine Transmissible venereal tumour (TVT) is usually a sexually transmitted neoplasm of external genitalia of dogs. In bitch, it is located on vagina. Transmissible venereal tumour was diagnosed on the basis of clinical signs and cell cytology. For the treatment, chemotherapy (vincristine sulfate at a dose of 0.025 mg/kg body weight) was done for two occasions at weekly interval. Multivitamin was also given for five days. The bitch completely recovered after two episodes of chemotherapy.*

Keywords: chemotherapy, cytology, bitch, CTVT, vincristine sulfate.

INTRODUCTION

Canine Transmissible Venereal Tumour (CTVT) is a disease of external genitalia of both male and female dogs. Venereal granuloma, infectious sarcoma, transmissible sarcoma, transmissible lymphosarcoma, canine condyloma are the synonyms of this disease (Dameski et al., 2018). This tumour appear as a cauliflower like pedunculate, multilobulated, nodular mass which is benign in nature and affects mainly canine species (Isabel et al., 2005). In male canines CTVT is located on penis or prepuce while in female this is seen in vagina or labia. Transmission of disease from one dog to another occurs through coitus (Stockmann et al., 2011). Extra genital occurs due to sniffing and licking of affected area (Komnenou et al., 2015). Metastasis is reported in immunocompromised dog and young pup. In metastatic form tumor may spread to pituitary gland, brain, liver, inguinal lymph node (Mukaratirwa & Gruys, 2003). Normal somatic cells

in canine have 78 chromosomes, but in tumorous cell chromosomes number ranges from 57 to 59 (Thomas et. Al. , 2009). Histopathological study is best diagnostic tool for CTVT. Chemotherapy, surgery, radiotherapy, and immunotherapy are the treatment of CTVT. Chemotherapy is most effective treatment (Abeka, 2019).

CASE DESCRIPTION

A Pomeranian breed bitch weighing 2.3 kg and approximately 4 years old was presented to Veterinary Clinical Complex, College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry, Acharya Narendra Deva University of Agriculture & Technology, Kumarganj, Ayodhya with a complaint of cauliflower like mass protruding out from its genital opening and red discharge from it. Earlier this case was treated by local paravet with calcium therapy.

Fig-1: Venereal tumor mass with bloody discharge

Physical examination of bitch revealed normal heart rate (92 beats/Minute), pulse rate (87 beats/Minutes), rectal temperature (102.4°F) and capillary refill time was less than 2 seconds. A pedunculated cauliflower mass with slight bleeding was protruded from genital opening (Fig:1).

Diagnosis was done on the basis of physical examination and cytological examination. On cytological examination, round or ovoid cell with bright cytoplasm and many vacuoles were found (Fig:2).

Fig-2: Cell cytology of canine transmissible venereal tumor showing large vacuolated tumor cells

Fig-3: After second injection of vincristine sulfate

The bitch was given an injection of vincristine sulfate at a dose of 0.025 mg/kg body weight intravenously every week for two occasions. For better health conditions multivitamin was provided for 5 days. Complete regression of tumour

was seen after second injection of vincristine sulfate (Fig:3).

DISCUSSION

Aim of treatment should be based on reducing tumor mass. Chemotherapeutic drugs such as cyclophosphamide, methotrexate, vincristine are used, but most popular drug is vincristine sulfate (Mukaratirwa & Gruys, 2003). Vincristine is cytotoxic. It interacts with tubulin and disrupt the microtubule function, mainly mitotic spindle apparatus, that leads metaphase arrest (Himes, 1991). Vincristine has some side effects along with therapeutic effect. Increase in liver enzymes after injection of vincristine shows cytotoxic effects of chemotherapy on liver (Camacho and Laus, 1989). Increase in creatinine, blood urea nitrogen and urea levels shows transient renal dysfunction after chemotherapy (Eleanor and David, 1982). These conditions increase chance of bacterial and parasitic infection.

CONCLUSION

Canine Transmissible Venereal Tumor is mostly seen in genitalia of canids. Immunocompromised animal are most susceptible to this disease. Cell cytology is best tool for diagnosis. Surgical intervention and chemotherapy with Vincristine sulfate @ 0.025 mg/kg body weight at weekly interval are the best treatment.

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